

**MEASURING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING
OPTIMIZATION ON BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI
FACEBOOK PAGE**

**WRITTEN BY:
RAISSA ARIFIA
NIM. S. 1317.326**

**ISLAMIC BUSINESS
AND MANAGEMENT PROGRAM
TAZKIA UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF ISLAMIC
ECONOMICS (STEI TAZKIA)
2018 M / 1439 H**

**MEASURING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING
OPTIMIZATION ON BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI
FACEBOOK PAGE**

Written to Complete Graduation Prerequisite of Islamic Business and
Management Program at STEI Tazkia

**WRITTEN BY:
RAISSA ARIFIA
NIM. S. 1317.326**

**ISLAMIC BUSINESS
AND MANAGEMENT PROGRAM
TAZKIA UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF ISLAMIC
ECONOMICS (STEI TAZKIA)
2018 M / 1439 H**

BACHELOR THESIS STATEMENT OF AUTHENCITY

I hereby stated that the bachelor thesis titled “**Measuring Social Media Marketing Optimization on Bank Syariah Mandiri Facebook Page**” along with all of its contents are works of my own, and I do not plagiarize or quote in ways that are not in accordance to the ethics of science. With this statement, I am ready to bear any penalties imposed on me if later found violation of scientific ethics in my work or if there was claim from the other party about the originality of my work.

Bogor, 30 September 2018

Stated by,

Raissa Arifia

S.1317.326

SUPERVISOR APPROVAL

Bachelor thesis titled **“MEASURING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING OPTIMIZATION ON BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI FACEBOOK PAGE”** which was written by:

Name : Raissa Arifia

NIM : S.1317.326

Study Program : Islamic Business and Management

Has been approved by the supervisor as one of graduation prerequisite in Islamic Business and Management Study Program of STEI Tazkia Bogor.

Bogor, 30 September 2018

Supervisor,

.....
(Sujana, M.M.)

ABSTRACT

Name : Raissa Arifia
NIM : S.1317.326
Major : Islamic Business and Management
Title : Measuring Social Media Marketing Optimization on Bank Syariah Mandiri Facebook Page

In the last few decades the significance growth of Islamic Banking has been rapidly changed. Since 1970s, their assets have been expanding dynamically and in the 2nd half of 2014 reached 1476.2 billion USD. One of the reasons why Indonesia Islamic bank is still running behind other country in terms of development and asset ownership is the lack of public understanding. Present in 1999, Bank Syariah Mandiri is currently an Islamic bank with the largest market share in the Islamic banking industry. Bank Syariah Mandiri also leads the online market by having more than 72.000 followers on their Official Facebook Page. In this research author would like to do a research about how optimal it is for Islamic bank, in this case Bank Syariah Mandiri, to use Facebook page as a part of their social media marketing process. The research will be done by comparing the correlation between each independent variable to the dependent variable using multiple linear regression statistic method. This study was conducted to measure the optimization of Facebook Page as Social Media Marketing done by Bank Syariah Mandiri by measuring the correlation between Social Media Advertising Variables from the EPIC Model by Nielsen, as the independent variable which consist of Empathy, Persuasion, Impact and Communication, to Social Media Engagement variable which is engagement rate as the dependent variable. The result shows us that there's still a lot of room to improve to optimize the social media marketing strategy done by Bank Syariah Mandiri to increase the engagement rate and social media advertising success on Facebook Page.

Keywords: Islamic Bank, Social Media Marketing, Social Media Optimization, Facebook

ABSTRAK

Nama : Raissa Arifia
NIM : S.1317.326
Jurusan : Manajemen dan Bisnis Islam
Judul : Measuring Social Media Marketing Optimization on Bank Syariah Mandiri Facebook Page

Dalam beberapa dekade terakhir, pertumbuhan signifikan perbankan syariah telah berubah dengan cepat. Sejak tahun 1970-an, aset perbankan syariah telah berkembang secara dinamis dan pada paruh kedua tahun 2014 mencapai 1.476,2 miliar USD. Salah satu alasan bank syariah Indonesia masih tertinggal dari negara lain dalam hal pengembangan dan kepemilikan aset adalah kurangnya pemahaman publik. Hadir pada tahun 1999, Bank Syariah Mandiri saat ini merupakan bank Islam dengan pangsa pasar terbesar dalam industri perbankan Islam. Bank Syariah Mandiri juga memimpin pasar online dengan memiliki lebih dari 72.000 pengikut di halaman *Facebook* resmi mereka. Dalam penelitian ini penulis ingin melakukan penelitian tentang seberapa optimal bagi bank syariah, dalam hal ini Bank Syariah Mandiri, untuk menggunakan halaman *Facebook* sebagai bagian dari proses pemasaran media sosial. Penelitian ini akan dilakukan dengan membandingkan korelasi antara masing-masing variabel independen terhadap variabel dependen menggunakan metode statistik regresi linier berganda. Penelitian ini dilakukan untuk mengukur optimalisasi *Facebook Page* sebagai media *Social Media Marketing* yang dilakukan oleh Bank Syariah Mandiri dengan mengukur korelasi antara variabel *Social Media Advertising* dari Model EPIC oleh Nielsen, sebagai variabel independen yang terdiri dari *empathy*, *persuasion*, *impact* dan *communication*, untuk variabel *Social Media Engagement* yang merupakan *engagement rate* sebagai variabel dependen. Hasilnya menunjukkan bahwa masih ada banyak ruang untuk meningkatkan untuk mengoptimalkan strategi pemasaran media sosial yang dilakukan oleh Bank Syariah Mandiri untuk meningkatkan *engagement rate* dan keberhasilan iklan media sosial di Halaman Facebook.

Kata kunci: Bank Islam, Pemasaran Media Sosial, Pengoptimalan Media Sosial, Facebook

**PAGE OF PUBLICATION CONSENT STATEMENT
FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES**

As a part of academic community of STEI Tazkia, author of the undersigned:

Name : Raissa Arifia

Student ID : S.1317.326

Study Program : Islamic Business Management

Category : Bachelor Thesis

For the sake of the development of science, the author agreed to give STEI Tazkia Non Exclusive Royalty-Free Right Statements of the bachelor thesis titled:

**“MEASURING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING OPTIMIZATION ON
BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI FACEBOOK PAGE”**

along with existing instruments (if needed). With this Non Exclusive Royalty-Free Right statement, STEI Tazkia is entitled to keep, to transfer, to format, to maintain, to manage in the form of database and publish as long as the author name included as the writer and the copyright owner.

This statement is made by the author truthfully.

Bogor, 30 September 2018

Stated by,

(Raissa Arifia)

ARABIC-ENGLISH ROMANIZATION GUIDELINES

Arabic	Roman	Arabic	Roman	Arabic	Roman
ا	A	س	S	ل	L
ب	B	ش	Sh	م	M
ت	T	ص	Ṣ	ن	N
ث	Th	ض	Ḍ	و	W
ج	J	ط	Ṭ	هـ	H
ح	Ḥ	ظ	Ẓ	ء	'
خ	Kh	ع	' (ayn)	ي	Y
د	D	غ	Gh		
ذ	Dh	ف	F		
ر	R	ق	Q		
ز	Z	ك	K		

Notes:

Diftongs written as : أو = aw, أو = û, أي = ay, إي = î

The signs listed below are frequently omitted from unvocalized Arabic writing and printing; their presence or absence must then be inferred. They are represented in romanization according to the following rules:

a) ء (hamzah)

In initial position, whether at the beginning of a word, following a prefixed preposition or conjunction, or following the definite article, ء is not represented in romanization. When medial or final, ء is romanized as ' (alif).

asad أسد mu'tamar مؤتمر

uns أنس mas'alah مسألة

ء, when replaced by the sign ٱ (waṣlah) and then known as hamzat al-waṣl, is not represented in romanization.

b) ٱ (waṣlah)

Like initial ء, is not represented in romanization. When the alif which supports waṣlah belongs to the article ال, the initial vowel of the article is romanized a. In other words, beginning with hamzat al-waṣl, the initial vowel is romanized i.

al-istidrāk الإستدراك

c) ~ (maddah)

Initial ٲ is romanized ā.

ālah 

Medial ٲ, when it represents the phonetic combination 'ā, is so romanized.

ta'ālīf 

~ is otherwise not represented in romanization.

khulafā' 

d)  (shaddah or tashdīd)

Over :

, representing the combination of long vowel plus consonant, is romanized ūw.

'adūw 

, representing the combination of diphthong plus consonant, is Romanized aww.

Shawwāl 

Over :

Medial , representing the combination of long vowel plus consonant, is romanized īy.

al-Miṣrīyah 

Final  is romanized ī.

Medial and final , representing the combination of diphthong plus consonant, is romanized ayy.

ayyām 

Over other letters,  is represented in romanization by doubling the letter or digraph concerned.

e)  (Tanwīn)

Tanwīn may take the written form ,  (), or , romanized un, an, and in, respectively. Tanwīn is normally disregarded in romanization, however. It is indicated in the following cases:

When it occurs in indefinite nouns derived from defective roots.

qāḍin 

When it indicates the adverbial use of a noun or adjective.

ṭab'an 

wa-al-muftariq ṣuq'an 

FOREWORD

Assalamu'alaikum Warahmatullahi Wabarakaatuh

Praise and gratitude bestowed upon Allah SWT. The Most Gracious, and the most merciful.

As a student majoring in Marketing, I have special interest toward digital and social media marketing. I've been taking certification in digital and social media marketing by Markplus this year to deepen my basic understanding about it. Turns out, digital and social media marketing wasn't as easy as people used to perceive. I used to think that social media marketing is just like basic marketing, the only difference is, it's online. After I learnt from my certification program, I learned that it's more than just marketing at the different media. It's a new art of marketing where you can be more engaging with your customer. Where you can be there for your customer virtually for 24 hours. It's like a store that opens 7/24. It's a whole new level of marketing. By this reason, I'm interested in examining how big companies apply digital and social media marketing in their marketing process. I'm curious on how digital and social media marketing affects a corporate image.

This research was conducted because I feel like Social Media Marketing hasn't been taken seriously by Islamic Bank in Indonesia, in this case, Bank Syariah Mandiri. The first thing that came to my mind when I first saw their Facebook page is: automated. It's not entirely a bad thing, but timing and content should also be considered to avoid spam and to make sure the content is engaging the audience.

This bachelor thesis is written as one of the prerequisite to complete the study in Islamic Business and Management Study Program, at STEI Tazkia, focused in Islamic Marketing Management. I took more time than my friends, but I love every second I spend making this bachelor thesis, and everything's worth it. I worked so hard for it and I'm proud of myself. And I'm really happy I did it.

I wanted to say thank you to:

1. Allah SWT. Without His mercy and blessings, I wouldn't be able to finish this bachelor thesis.
2. My parents who has given me infinite love and support.
3. Mr. Sujana as my supervisor, who has guided me through everything in the process of this bachelor thesis writing. Thank you for the time and patience while supervising me.
4. My friends. Thank you for the emotional support, motivation. You guys are the sugar of my cup of tea.

May Allah grant all of these people His blessings and jannah. Thank you for all of the help, guidance, and support I received during this thesis writing process.

I hope that this report can be an inspiration to readers to learn more about digital and social media marketing. I'm really open to every critic and opinion readers might have in mind about my report.

Wassalamu'alaikum Warahmatullahi Wabarakaatuh

Bogor, 30 September 2018

Raissa Arifia
S.1317.326

TABLE OF CONTENT

BACHELOR THESIS STATEMENT OF AUTHENCITY	iii
SUPERVISOR APPROVAL	iv
ABSTRACT.....	v
ABSTRAK.....	vi
PAGE OF PUBLICATION CONSENT STATEMENT FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES	viii
ARABIC-ENGLISH ROMANIZATION GUIDELINES	ix
FOREWORD	xi
TABLE OF CONTENT	xiii
TABLE OF FIGURES	xvi
TABLE OF TABLES	xvii
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Research Background	1
1.2 Problems	2
1.3 Research Limitation	2
1.4 Research Purposes	2
1.5 Research Benefit	3
1.6 Writing Systematics	3
CHAPTER II: THEORETICAL BASE.....	5
2.1 Conceptual Description.....	5
2.1.1 Marketing.....	5
2.1.2 Social Media	11
2.1.3 Facebook	13
2.1.4 Social Media Marketing.....	14
2.1.5 EPIC Model	15

2.1.6	Bank	17
2.2	Previous Research	18
2.3	Theoretical Framework	23
2.4	Hypothesis Development	23
CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY		24
3.1	Research Type.....	24
3.2	Data Type and Source	24
3.3	Data Collection Technique.....	25
3.4	Population and Sample.....	25
3.5	Operational Variable	26
3.6	Sampling Technique	27
3.7	Data Analysis Technique	27
3.7.1	Instrumental Test.....	27
3.7.2	Classical Assumption Test.....	29
3.7.3	Multiple Regression Analysis	31
CHAPTER IV: FINDINGS		33
4.1	General Description of Research Object.....	33
4.1.1	History of Bank Syariah Mandiri.....	33
4.1.2	Bank Syariah Mandiri Business Field.....	34
4.1.3	Bank Syariah Mandiri Online Presence	36
4.2	Respondent Profile Index.....	40
4.2.1	Gender of Respondents	40
4.2.2	Age	41
4.2.3	Occupation	41
4.3	Respondent Answer Index	42
4.3.1	Empathy	42
4.3.2	Persuasion	43
4.3.3	Impact	44

4.3.4	Communication.....	44
4.3.5	Engagement Rate	45
4.4	Instrumental Test	45
4.4.1	Validity Test.....	45
4.4.2	Reliability Test.....	46
4.5	Classic Assumption Test.....	47
4.5.1	Multicollinearity Test.....	47
4.5.2	Normality Test	48
4.5.3	Heteroscedasticity Test	48
4.6	Determination Coefficient.....	49
4.7	Hypothesis Testing.....	50
4.7.1	Partial Test	50
4.7.2	Simultaneous Test.....	52
4.8	Findings.....	53
4.8.1	The Correlation between Empathy to Engagement Rate	53
4.8.2	The Correlation between Persuasion to Engagement Rate	55
4.8.3	The Correlation between Impact to Engagement Rate.....	56
4.8.4	The Correlation between Communication to Engagement Rate	57
CHAPTER V: CONCLUSION.....		58
5.1	Conclusion	58
5.2	Research Limitations	58
5.3	Suggestions.	59
BIBLIOGRAPHY		61

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1 9 Core Elements of Marketing.....	6
Figure 2.2 4 Zones of Social Media.....	12
Figure 2.3 Theoretical Framework.....	23
Figure 4.1 Bank Syariah Mandiri Facebook Page	38
Figure 4.2 Bank Syariah Mandiri Twitter Page	39
Figure 4.3 Bank Syariah Mandiri Instagram Page	40
Figure 4.4 Gender of Respondents.....	40
Figure 4.5 Age of Respondents.....	41
Figure 4.6 Occupation of Respondents	41

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 4.1 Respondent Answer Index Classes	42
Table 4.2 Respondent Answer Index - Empathy	42
Table 4.3 Respondent Answer Index - Persuasion	43
Table 4.4 Respondent Answer Index - Impact.....	44
Table 4.5 Respondent Answer Index - Communication	44
Table 4.6 Respondent Answer Index - Engagement Rate.....	45
Table 4.7 Validity Test Result	46
Table 4.8 Reliability Test Result.....	47
Table 4.9 Multicollinearity Test Result	47
Table 4.10 Normality Test Result.....	48
Table 4.11 Heteroscedasticity Test Result.....	49
Table 4.12 Coefficient of Determination (R^2) Test Result.....	49
Table 4.13 Partial Test Result	51
Table 4.14 Simultaneous Test Result.....	52

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

In the last few decades the significance growth of Islamic Banking has been rapidly changed. Since 1970s, their assets have been expanding dynamically and in the 2nd half of 2014 reached 1476.2 billion USD. Islamic banks operate in over 75 countries, not only in Islamic countries, but also in countries in which Muslim is minority, such as the United Kingdom, the United States of America, and France. However, Indonesia, even though being the largest country with most Muslim population in the world, was relatively late in introducing Islamic banking. It was almost 20 years after the development of the modern Islamic banking in the world that the first Islamic bank was built in this country. Until now, the growth of Islamic banking in Indonesia, in comparison with Iran, Malaysia and the Middle East countries, is rather slow. In 2014, assets of Islamic banks operating in Indonesia accounted for 1.39%, which gave Indonesia 9th place in world rank. The first three places were taken by Iran (40,21% share), Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (18,57%), and Malaysia (9,56%) (Islamic Financial Board, 2015)

One of the reasons why Indonesia Islamic bank is still running behind other country in terms of development and asset ownership is the lack of public understanding and awareness. (Financial Service Authority, Republic of Indonesia, 2015) This problem needs to be fixed really soon to be able to develop Islamic bank in Indonesia better.

The marketing environment has changed significantly in the last decade. The penetration and usage of the internet and social media is growing. According to a survey conducted by APJII (Asosiasi Penyelenggara Jasa Internet Indonesia) in 2016, the number of internet users in Indonesia reached 132,7 million users. The survey also shows that 97,4% of Indonesian internet user access social media, in which, the most used social media is Facebook (54%). This shows that social media, specifically Facebook is a great place for marketing

Present in 1999, Bank Syariah Mandiri is currently an Islamic bank with the largest market share in the Islamic banking industry. The market share includes assets, third party funds and financing. Market share of assets per December 2017 is 20.73%, Third Party Funds 23.27% and Financing 21.24%.

Bank Syariah Mandiri also leads the online market by having more than 72.000 followers on their Official Facebook Page. In this research author would like to do a research about how optimal it is for Islamic bank, in this case Bank Syariah Mandiri, to use Facebook page as a part of their social media marketing process. The research will be done by comparing the correlation between each independent variable to the dependent variable using multiple linear regression statistic method.

1.2 Problems

The problems that are going to be researched in this study are:

1. Does empathy affect engagement rate?
2. Does persuasion affect engagement rate?
3. Does impact affect engagement rate?
4. Does communication affect engagement rate?
5. Do empathy, persuasion, impact and communication affect engagement rate?

1.3 Research Limitation

This research is limited to measure the optimization of social media marketing in Facebook that has been implemented by Bank Syariah Mandiri, by measuring the correlation between each independent variable (EPIC) to the dependent variable (engagement rate) using multiple linear regression statistic method.

1.4 Research Purposes

The purposes of this research are:

1. Researching the correlation between empathy to engagement rate
2. Researching the correlation between persuasion to engagement rate

3. Researching the correlation between impact to engagement rate
4. Researching the correlation between communication to engagement rate
5. Researching the correlation between empathy, persuasion, impact, and communication to engagement rate

1.5 Research Benefit

Benefits that are going to be derived from this research are:

1. The results of this study are expected to provide knowledge for Islamic banks' management regarding the usefulness of social media marketing for Islamic banks' marketing process.
2. For authors interested in researching the same study it is hoped that this research can be used as a reference and a comparison material for further research. And can add and expand knowledge about social media marketing and Islamic banks' marketing.

1.6 Writing Systematics

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

The first chapter explains the background of problems, problem formulation, research objectives, research benefits, and systematics of writing.

CHAPTER II: THEORY BASIS

The second chapter describes the theoretical basis and the literature used as reference comparisons to discuss problems, including marketing, social media, bank, EPIC model, prior research, and frameworks theoretical thinking.

CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The third chapter describes the research methodology consisting of the types and sources of data used in this study, the method of collecting research data used, the identification of research variables. Explain the method of data analysis which includes: type or technique of analysis and mechanism of use of tools in research.

CHAPTER IV: FINDINGS

The fourth chapter describes the results obtained from the research undertaken by the writing and its findings.

CHAPTER V: CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The fifth chapter explains the conclusions the authors derive from the results of the research, and suggestions on the results of the research to be provided by the authors.

CHAPTER II: THEORETICAL BASE

2.1 Conceptual Description

2.1.1 Marketing

Marketing is the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large. (American Marketing Association, 2013)

Marketing is the science and art of exploring, creating, and delivering value to satisfy the needs of a target market at a profit. Marketing identifies unfulfilled needs and desires. It defines measures and quantifies the size of the identified market and the profit potential. It pinpoints which segments the company is capable of serving best and it designs and promotes the appropriate products and services. (Kotler & Keller, 2012)

Marketing is the process through which you create and keep customers. Marketing is the matchmaker between what your business is selling and what your customers are buying. It covers all the steps that are involved to tailor your products, messages, distribution, customer service, and all other business actions to meet the desires of your most important business asset: your customer. Marketing is a win-win partnership between your business and its market. It isn't about talking to your customers; it's about talking with them. It relies on two-way communication between your business and your buyer. (Schenck, 2005)

According to Kartajaya, (2007a) there are 9 core element of marketing, which consist of 3 main core, Strategy, Tactic, and Value. Each main core has 3 sub-cores:

Strategy : Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning

Tactic : Selling, Marketing Mix, Differentiation

Value : Brand, Service, Process

Figure II.1 9 Core Elements of Marketing

Segmentation

According to (Middleton & Clarke, 2001) segmentation may now be defined as the process of dividing a total market such as all customers, or a market sector into subgroups or segments for marketing management purposes. Its purpose is to facilitate more cost-effective marketing through the formulation, promotion, and delivery of purpose designed products that satisfy the identified needs of target groups. In other words, segmentation is justified on the grounds of achieving greater efficiency in the supply of products to meet identified demand and increased cost effectiveness in the marketing process. The primary bases for segmentation include demography, geography, behavior, lifestyle, personality, and benefits sought (Park & Yoon, 2009).

Targeting

Company realized that it may not serve all segments, because the limited resource owned, so companies should decide which segments become targets . (Kotler, 2000) There is some target market decision-making pattern:

Single Segment Concentration, election on only one single segment, the company gives all its effort only to concentrate on one particular segment.

- 1 Selective Specialization, the company selects a limited number of segments, based on the goals and resources owned by the company.
- 2 Product Specialization, the company concentrates on producing certain products it sells in some segments.
- 3 Market Specialization, the company concentrates in serving the many needs of a particular consumer group.
- 4 Full Market Coverage, the company strives to serve the entire group of customers with all the products they need. (Kotler, 2000)

Positioning

When a company decides its market segment, they must know what position they want to have. The position strategy is based on consumer's important characters and needs. When a company is positioning itself, it needs to know that positioning involves implementation the brand's unique benefits and differentiation in customer's minds. (Kotler & Armstrong, 2001) Positioning is a necessary concept, first because all choices are comparative, and so it makes sense to start off by starting in the area where a company is strongest, secondly because in marketing, perception is reality. (Uggla, 2006) Furthermore, positioning is not about the product itself, but what the buyer thinks about the product or the organization. (Fill, 2002)

Brand

The term "brand" can be defined as a name of a brand that identifies a certain product, manufacturer or distributor. In comparison to a brand, a strong brand is a product, service, person or place that can be identified and improved in the way that the consumer or buyer gains essential, unique added values which meet their needs in the best possible way. (Law &

Pallister, 2009) In addition, success of a brand results from being able to maintain added values in spite of competitors' actions. (De Chernatony & McDonald, 1992) On the other hand, American Marketing Association (AMA) defines brand as a name, term, design, symbol, or any other characteristic that clearly makes an attribute or quality of a good or service distinguishable or recognizable. AMA adds that brand can determine seller's product or service, multiple products or services or all the products or services of a particular seller. AMA specifies that brand's legal term is trademark and broadens the definition of the term "brand" to be a customer experience that can be described as a group of ideas and images that often refer to a symbol, a name, slogan or a logo, for instance.

Service

A service is a process consisting of a series of more or less intangible activities that normally, but not necessarily always, takes place in interactions between the customer and service employees and/or physical resources or goods and/or systems of the service provider, which are provided as solutions to customer problems (Grönroos, 2007). For instance, successful marketing models require the inclusion of the interactions between the service provider and the customer during the consumption process as an integrated part of marketing. Service management and marketing depend on the inclusion and participation of the customer in the service process. Services feature are mainly specific to the type of the service, but in general services have three basic characteristics:

- 1 Services are processes consisting of activities or a series of activities.
- 2 Services are at least to some extent produced and consumed simultaneously.
- 3 The customer participates as a co-producer in the service production process at least to some extent (Grönroos, 2007).

Process

In the marketing concept, the process reflects the quality, cost (cost), and delivery of the product (delivery) from the company to its customers. The quality of the company's products and services is the result of a good process; which starts from production to delivery to customers in a timely, effective, and cost-efficient manner. So, companies must understand the process. That way, the company can have a strong competitiveness in the face of its competitors. In the context of quality, the process is how the company is able to create a system that ultimately can provide more value for customers. Therefore, companies need to pay more attention to supply-chain, from raw material production process to finished goods. In fact, the process actually requires the company to be the captain of supply-chain. Therefore, it takes a strong commitment from the company to create a better value. And of course, your company will be able to reduce the erosion activity in the company's value. (Kartajaya, 2007a)

Selling

Selling is how to create long-term relationships with customers through a company's products or services. In this case, selling means a tactic that can integrate companies, customers, and relationships between the two. (Kartajaya, 2007b)

Differentiation

It has long been acknowledged that service differentiation through effective market segmentation ensures survivability of the firm in the long run (Chan, 2000). Much literature has propounded the importance of service differentiation and market segmentation to appeal to groups of buyers for profitability (Aaker, 2008; Johnson, Scholes, & Whittington, 2008). A business must recognize that it cannot appeal to all customers in the marketplace. It has to identify the different groups of buyers with similar needs and requirements so that it can serve each group separately and

effectively. In addition the availability of a firm's resources is often limited (Lynch, 2000) and this necessitates market segmentation to better target customers' needs.

Marketing Mix

The concept of the marketing mix was reportedly introduced by Neil Borden in his presidential address to the AMA in 1953. He got his idea from James Culliton, who described the business executive as somebody who combines different ingredients. The term "marketing mix" therefore referred to the mixture of elements useful in pursuing a certain market response. (Waterschoot & Bulte, 1992) The marketing mix has been defined as the "set of marketing tools that the firm uses to pursue its marketing objectives in the target market"(Kotler, 2000) Marketing mix consists of Price, Placement, Product and Promotion (McCarthy, 1960)

Promotion

Promotion is advertising a product or brand, generating sales, and creating brand loyalty. It is one of the four basic elements of the market mix, which includes the four P's: price, product, promotion, and place. (McCarthy, 1960) Sales promotion consists of a diverse collection of incentive tools, mostly short-term, designed to stimulate quicker and/or greater purchase of a particular product by consumers or the trade. (Kotler, 2000) the heart of sales promotion is represented by the value that it adds to a product or a service. This value may be different according to different types of promotions: an extra free product, money saving, a gift or a sample, the opportunity to win a prize etc. thus in general by something new, added to the usual product that consumers would not get under normal circumstances. The added value therefore provides an extra incentive to buy, an inducement that changes temporarily the perception of the price and the value of the product. It is supposed to provide a direct impact on behavior, a sort of acceleration to the selling process that pushes the consumer to a faster purchase. (Conte, 2012)

Promotion in Islamic Marketing, should be done considering 4 aspects, there are: Siddiq (Honesty), Amanah (Trustworthy, and Credible), Fatanah (Smart) and Tabligh (Communicative) (Sula & Kartajaya, 2006), these has also been mentioned in Qur'an Surah Al-Ahzab ayah 70 and 71:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اتَّقُوا اللَّهَ وَقُولُوا قَوْلًا سَدِيدًا (70) يُصْلِحْ لَكُمْ أَعْمَالَكُمْ وَيَغْفِرْ لَكُمْ
ذُنُوبَكُمْ وَمَنْ يُطِيعِ اللَّهَ وَرَسُولَهُ فَقَدْ فَازَ فَوْزًا عَظِيمًا (71)

“O you who have believed, fear Allah and speak words of appropriate justice. He will [then] amend for you your deeds and forgive you your sins. And whoever obeys Allah and His Messenger has certainly attained a great attainment.” (Q.S.33:70-71)

Allah also said in al-Qur'an al-Kareem, that we Muslims have to communicate using قَوْلًا بَلِيغًا (far-reaching word), in the other words, we have to communicate effectively that it reaches people soul, and mind. It shows that an effective and straightforward communication is important. It is written in Qur'an Surah Al-Imraan ayah 63:

أُولَئِكَ الَّذِينَ يَعْلَمُ اللَّهُ مَا فِي قُلُوبِهِمْ فَأَعْرِضْ عَنْهُمْ وَعِظْهُمْ وَقُلْ لَهُمْ فِي أَنفُسِهِمْ قَوْلًا بَلِيغًا

“Those are the ones of whom Allah knows what is in their hearts, so turn away from them but admonish them and speak to them a far-reaching word.” (Q.S. 3:63)

2.1.2 Social Media

(Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) describe social media as “a group of Internet based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content.” Web 2.0 technologies on the Social Web permit two-way conversations with consumers enabling brands to listen to consumers and respond (Fournier & Avery, 2011). Consumers and organizations alike

are increasingly using the web to discuss, share, and collaborate (Jones, 2010).

There are 4 zones of social media according to its use (Tuten & Solomon, 2014) :

Figure II.2 4 Zones of Social Media

- **Social Community**

Channels of social media focusing on relationships the common activities people participate in with others who share the same interest of identification. It includes social networking sites (SNS), message boards, forums, and wikis. Example: Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn

- **Social Publishing**

Sites which aid in dissemination of content to an audience. It includes blogs, micro sharing sites, microblogging sites, media sharing sites, social bookmarking, and news sites. Example: Pinterest, BlogSpot, and Tumblr.

- **Social Entertainment**

Social entertainment encompasses channels and vehicles that offer opportunities for play and enjoyment. It includes social games, socially enabled console games, alternate reality games, virtual worlds, and entertainment communities. Example: League of Legends, Clash of Clan, and FarmVille.

- **Social Commerce**

The use of social media to assist in the online buying and selling of products and services. It includes reviews and ratings, deal sites, deal aggregators, social shopping markets, and social storefronts. Example: BukaLapak, Tokopedia, Shopee, Carousell, and OLX.

2.1.3 Facebook

Facebook is an American for-profit corporation and an online social media and social networking service based in Menlo Park, California. The Facebook website was launched on February 4, 2004, by Mark Zuckerberg, along with fellow Harvard College students and roommates, Eduardo Saverin, Andrew McCollum, Dustin Moskovitz and Chris Hughes. (Carlson, 2010) Facebook may be accessed by a large range of desktops, laptops, tablet computers, and smartphones over the Internet and mobile networks. After registering to use the site, users can create a user profile indicating their name, occupation, schools attended and so on. Users can add other users as "friends", exchange messages, post status updates and digital photos, share digital videos and links, use various software applications (apps), and receive notifications when others update their profiles or make posts. Additionally, users may join common-interest user groups organized by workplace, school, hobbies or other topics, and categorize their friends into lists such as "People From Work" or "Close Friends". In groups, editors can pin posts to top. Additionally, users can complain about or block unpleasant people. Because of the large volume of data that users submit to the service, Facebook has come under scrutiny for its privacy policies. Facebook makes most of its revenue from advertisements which appear onscreen, marketing access for its customers to its users and offering highly selective advertising opportunities. (Lanchester, 2017) Facebook, Inc. held its initial public offering (IPO) in February 2012, and began selling stock to the public three months later, reaching an original peak market capitalization of \$104 billion. On July 13, 2015, Facebook became the fastest company in the Standard & Poor's 500 Index to reach a market cap of \$250 billion. (Davis, 2015) Facebook has more than 2 billion monthly active

users as of June 2017. (Constine, 2017; Welch, 2017) As of April 2016, Facebook was the most popular social networking site in the world, based on the number of active user accounts.(Statista, 2017) Facebook classifies users from the ages of 13 to 18 as minors and therefore sets their profiles to share content with friends only.(Hajirmis, 2015)

2.1.4 Social Media Marketing

Social media has caused a significant change in the strategies and tools companies use for communicating with customers. Mangold & Faulds, 2009 argue that “social media combines characteristics of traditional IMC tools (companies talking to customers) with a highly magnified form of word-of-mouth (customers talking to one another) whereby marketing managers cannot control the content and frequency of such information.” Companies are limited in the amount of control they have over the content and distribution of information. Ignoring such user-generated content is not an option. Companies must be able to monitor and respond to conversation, both positive and negative, surrounding the brand. There are ways however, that companies can influence discussions in a way that is consistent with the organization’s mission (Mangold & Faulds, 2009). Social media marketing enables companies to achieve a better understanding of customer needs in order to build effective relationships. Social media marketing is the utilization of social media technologies, channels, and software to create, communicate, deliver, and exchange offerings that have value for an organization’s stakeholders. (Tuten & Solomon, 2014)

Social influence marketing (i.e., social media marketing) is a technique that employs social media (content created by everyday people using highly accessible and scalable technologies such as blogs, message boards, podcasts, microblogs, bookmarks, social networks, communities, wikis, and vlogs) and social influencers (everyday people who have an outsized influence on their peers by virtue of how much content they share online) to achieve an organization’s marketing and business needs. (Singh, 2010) Social media marketing is the process of gaining website traffic or

attention through social media sites. Social media marketing programs usually center on efforts to create content that attracts attention and encourages readers to share it across their social networks. The resulting electronic word of mouth (eWoM) refers to any statement consumers share via the Internet (e.g., web sites, social networks, instant messages, news feeds) about an event, product, service, brand or company. When the underlying message spreads from user to user and presumably resonates because it appears to come from a trusted, third-party source, as opposed to the brand or company itself. (Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2013)

Social media marketing is the use of both social media advertising and social media engagement to promote a brand's product or service. Social media advertising is the planning and buying of display ads on social websites such as Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, etc. These ads are targeted to specific users, yet they are passive in nature because people aren't actively looking for the information/service that a brand is providing. Social media engagement is comprised of content-rich social media postings, followed by in-depth and timely discussion/interaction with the followers of individual advertiser social media assets (Facebook, LinkedIn, etc.).

This provide us with an insight that to make an optimal social media marketing plan, social media advertising and social media engagement must go well together.

2.1.5 EPIC Model

EPIC Model is an advertising effectivity metric that is developed by AC Nielsen, a top marketing research company, E.P.I.C. determines there are four critical dimensions to measuring the effectiveness of advertising—Empathy, Persuasion, Impact, Communication—and for different advertising campaigns these dimensions take on different levels of importance, depending on the advertising objectives.

Empathy

In general, social media users understand the content of the information submitted ads on social media that initially had no emotional meaning to media users social. Consumer empathy needs to be improved through advertising to be attracted to understand the content of an advertisement issued by the company as fulfillment consumers' desires. By promoting through advertising will indirectly increase one's desire to understand the content of the ad and look for the ad.

Empathy involves consumer affection and cognition, affection and cognition refers to two types of internal psychological responses consumers to environmental stimuli and events that take place. Affection involves feeling, while cognition involves thinking affective. Feedback variations can be positive, negative, fun or not fun, and consumers can feel four types of affective responses of emotions, different feelings, moods and evaluations in intensity and power levels of improvisation. (Nasution & Suyanto, 2016)

Persuasion

Persuasion is a change that occurs to the trust of social media users, attitudes and wishes behave that caused a promotional communication from social media. Advertisements submitted need to be easy to understand and interesting so that consumer interest in the product increases and will arise feelings want to know more about a product that raises the attraction for consumers. (Nasution & Suyanto, 2016)

Impact

The desired impact of promotional results in social media is the increased knowledge of social media by looking at the frequency of activity of users opening social media and how often to visit social media. By using attractive ads through practical media such as social media will increase consumers' desire to search for information, and try products that interest them. Then, these ads will affect consumers to make product selection.

Communication

Communication focuses on the understanding of social media users as well as the power of impression left behind from the information provided on the ad.

The success of the implementation of the promotion strategy requires a two-stage communication model. The first stage occurs when the market creates promotional communication to encode a meaning. The second stage is decoding, that is, consumers enter and understand information in promotional communication and develop their personal interpretation of the meaning captured. (Durianto, 2003)

Engagement Rate

Engagement refers to the relevance of the Facebook Page to users and the actions they take when they visit the Page. You can measure engagement by taking a look at the types of activities users engage in, such as becoming a fan, writing on your timeline, liking or commenting on an update, uploading a photo or video, or mentioning your Page in status updates. (Porterfield, Khare, & Vahl, 2013)

Social media engagement (often abbreviated as SME) is the process by which online communications and the content you post online help you build connections with other people within online communities. Social media engagement involves the use of the tools of social media – social networks, for example – to build relationships with others that, ideally, result in some kind of reaction, interaction, or action. (Sherman & Smith, 2013)

2.1.6 Bank

The definition of ‘bank’ according to the UU Negara Republik Indonesia, No. 10 of 1998 dated November 10, 1998 on banking, referred to as a bank is a business entity that collects funds from the public in the form

of savings and distributes it to the community in the form of credit and or other forms in order improve the standard of living of many people.

From the definition of banks according to the UU Negara Republik Indonesia, No. 10 of 1998 can be concluded that the banking business includes three activities, namely raising funds, channeling funds, and provide other bank services. The activity of collecting and channeling funds is a principal activity of the bank while providing other bank services is only a supporting activity. The activities of raising funds, in the form of collecting funds from the public in the form of savings current accounts, savings, and deposits. Usually while being given such attractive services, interest and gifts as a stimulus for people to prefer to save. Activities channeled funds, in the form of lending to the community. While other banking services are provided to support the continuity of the main activities.

Islamic Bank

An Islamic banking and financial system exists to provide a variety of religiously acceptable financial services to the Muslim communities. In addition to this special function, the banking and financial institutions, like all other aspects of Islamic society, are expected to ‘contribute richly to the achievement of the major socio-economic goals of Islam’ (Chapra, 1985)

2.2 Previous Research

Research about social media marketing in Islamic bank, social media advertising and social media engagement has been conducted several times:

1. Research conducted by Arifia, 2016, “Social Media Optimization (SMO) to Improve Islamic Banks’ Marketing”, the sample used 12 Islamic banks in 2015. Social media nowadays has a really great role in online marketing. Not only to advertise the product of the company, but also to get more personal with the customer. Companies or in this case, Islamic Banks, are eager to get more customers by using social media. The study performed, based on public data analysis, and online survey results. To conclude, Islamic Banks in Indonesia can optimize

their social media further, in order to reach the target market more efficiently.

2. Research conducted by Aasheim & Stensønes, 2011, "Financial Institutions in Social Media; Deliver Traditional Services in New Channels. A Case Study Of Danske Bank", the social media used by the bank is Facebook. Through the task technology fit analysis, it turned out that Facebook is rich in terms of providing features that can benefit a bank in all of the four challenges; intangibility, accessibility, contactability and perishability. After looking at each of them separately, most of the subcategories defining media richness get a medium to high score in terms of fit.
3. Research conducted by Mitic & Kapoulas, 2012, "Understanding the role of social media in bank marketing", The purpose of this paper is to investigate the role of Web 2.0 and social media in relationship marketing (RM) in banking. The aim is to understand why some banks resist the Web 2.0 trend, how this is aligned with their RM approaches and what the alternative paths for advancing customer relations could be. The paper focuses on the practices of banks in the less-researched yet dynamically evolving South East European (SEE) region. Case studies also revealed insights on the possible tactics for social media engagement for banks. These include, first, creating interactive and relevant content; second, encouraging clients to interact with bank via online social networks; third, encouraging customers to actively contribute ideas to enhance bank's offers for mutual benefit; and finally, collaborating with online community to create awareness about social media programs.
4. Research conducted Chikandiwa, Contogiannis, & Edgar, 2013, "The adoption of social media marketing in South African banks", The purpose of this paper is to examine social media adoption models and social media implementation models being used by South African banks when adopting social media marketing. Challenges and opportunities faced are addressed in the paper. Social media is still at

its infancy level in South Africa. The ACCESS model and the OASIS model are the most commonly used implementation models in South African banks. Further to that, findings indicate that Facebook and Twitter are the main tools used by banks and they are used for reactive customer service and advertising. Legal and regulatory issues were identified as obstacles to the adoption of social media. All respondents agreed on the need to integrate social media with traditional media. This might be because South African customers are consumers of both the new and traditional media.

5. Research conducted by Goi, 2014, “The Impacts of Social Media on the Local Commercial Banks in Malaysia”, social media has an effective impact on banks, especially in terms of conversation, sharing, publishing and participation. Moreover, local commercial banks in Malaysia have been using social media to communicate with their customers. Specifically, banks in Malaysia are using social media for the purpose of engaging with their customers, especially to assist in new product development or product innovation; to enhance customer experience and service level; to build their organisation’s image; to implement promotion strategies; and to develop a transparency strategy.
6. Thesis done by, Wigmo & Wikström, 2010 “Social Media Marketing: What role can social media play as a marketing tool?” the purpose of this research is to analyze and explore how companies could use social media to promote themselves and improve their business to consumer relationship, this in order to develop a general set of recommendations. To fulfill the purpose they have used a qualitative research method with a held study approach. By studying both social media and marketing theories and combining these with interviews of social media consultants, they have managed to compile a set of recommendations for corporate social media usage. As a complement, they have observed some companies that use social media in order to

document and analyze how they use it, primarily to expand their understanding.

7. Study done by Sinha, Ahuja, & Medury, 2011 “Corporate blogs and internet marketing – Using consumer knowledge and emotion as strategic variables to develop consumer engagement”. They conceptualize an experiment to increase the knowledge level of a consumer, pertaining to brand, where they use a simulated lab environment where a set of consumers are exposed to a corporate brand blog for a fixed duration. The variation in levels of CBK is calculated. They further develop a research instrument to measure the emotion levels of consumers, pertaining to a brand, both before and after exposure to the corporate blog. Subsequent to this study, they attempt to find a correlation between variations in CBK and consumer brand emotion, which clearly indicates that as a consumer's knowledge about a product or brand increases, so does his emotional attachment with the brand. This subsequently increases the consumer adoption of, and relationship with the brand.
8. “The Influence Of Empathy And Self-Presentation On Engagement With Social Networking Website Posts” by Mayshak, Sharman, Zinkiewicz, & Hayley, n.d. examined associations between self-presentation, trait empathy, and engagement with social networking website (SNS) posts containing positive, neutral, or negative sentiment. It was hypothesized that participants would show lower engagement with negatively valenced posts than with positively valenced posts due to the increased cognitive and emotional effort associated with responding. It was also hypothesized that trait empathy would predict participants’ engagement with SNS content. Participants’ motivation for engaging with posts was also investigated through qualitative measures. Ninety-seven participants (aged 18-63 years; $M = 26.32$, $SD = 8.68$) interacted with a simulated SNS environment and described the aspects of posts that encouraged their engagement. Participants then completed trait empathy and social

desirability measures. Results showed that participants liked, shared, and commented on more negatively valenced posts than positively valenced posts; they also hid more negatively valenced posts than positively valenced or neutral posts. Age predicted engagement with negatively valenced posts; age and trait empathy predicted engagement with neutral posts, and trait empathy predicted engagement with positively valenced posts. Participants described a number of aspects that encouraged them to engage with posts, including personal connections with the poster, humor or novelty of topic, personal interest in the topic, concern for the poster, positive experience by the poster, and self-presentation concerns. Results suggest that both self-presentation efforts and trait empathy can influence the type and amount of engagement users have with emotion laden SNS content.

9. Study conducted by R. Stefko, R. Bacik and I. Fedorko, titled "Facebook Content Analysis of Banks Operating on Slovakia Market" stated that this article uses content analysis to identify the extent of users' involvement in the corporate communication on the social network Facebook. This article focuses on the Facebook pages of the largest banking institutions operating in Slovakia - regarding the volume of their total assets in 2012. The analysis shows that the criterion for the success of the post on the largest social network Facebook is an effort to maximize the involvement of users in the corporate communication through the indicators and instruments "likes", comments and share. The positive values of correlation coefficients indicate the importance of users engaging in activities of companies. Therefore, the possibility of sharing users' posts and the subsequent impact on the number of "likes" seems to be highly important tool for raising the Engagement Rate.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

Figure II.3 Theoretical Framework

The development of increasingly advanced technology, especially the internet, provides facilities and all the ease with social media. One of them is Facebook. The rise of Facebook users makes it easy for its users to get information. The existing facilities on Facebook can be a place to advertise. With that the appearance of the ad "Bank Syariah Mandiri" on Facebook create a new pattern in advertising and form a new consumption patterns for consumers. This causes author to do the research on how optimal the social media marketing done by measuring the EPIC variables to Engagement Rate using Multiple Linear Regression Method.

2.4 Hypothesis Development

These are the hypothesis of the study:

H₁ : Empathy positively affects engagement rate

H₂ : Persuasion positively affects engagement rate

H₃ : Impact positively affects engagement rate

H₄ : Communication positively affects engagement rate

H₅ : Empathy, persuasion, impact and communication positively affects engagement rate

CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Type

The type of this research is in the form of quantitative research. Quantitative research is a research that works with numbers, which data are tangible numbers (scores or values, frequency ratings) analyzed using statistics to answer specific research questions or hypotheses, and to predict that a particular variable affects other variables (Nazir, 2003). This research is also in the form of descriptive research. Descriptive research is a study that only describes the situation or event. These events do not seek or explain relationships, do not test hypotheses or make predictions. Descriptive research is intended for (Rakhmat, 2004):

1. Gathering actual information as well as details describing existing conditions.
2. Identify the problem or check the conditions and practices that apply.
3. Make a comparison or evaluation.
4. Determine what others are doing in the face of the same problem and learn from their experience to decide future plans and decisions.

Characteristics above are the references that will be used in conducting this research. In the process of this study, researchers will use questionnaires in searching primary data, which results in the numbers of respondents who considered the representation of the population.

3.2 Data Type and Source

All information obtained can be distinguished by source, there are:

Primary Data

Primary Data is data obtained straight from the main source either from individuals or institutions representatives such as the result of interview or the result of filling out a questionnaire commonly done by researcher (Umar, 2003).

In this study the data collected directly from the object of research in this case is the result of the questionnaire answers distributed to the respondents; the data will then be the main data to be analyzed

Secondary Data

Secondary data is primary data that has been processed further and presented, either by the primary data collector or by the company. This secondary data in the form of literature that support and add significant information for the research, which is written material in the form of books, journals, research reports, documents related to the fulfillment of information needs. (Sugiyono, 2008) mentions the benefits of using secondary data are to:

- a. Identify the problem
- b. Define the problem better
- c. Develop a problem approach
- d. Formulate appropriate research design
- e. Answer research questions and test some hypotheses
- f. Interpret the primary data becomes clearer

3.3 Data Collection Technique

Data collection methods are intended to obtain relevant, accurate and reliable information. The methods used include:

1. Method Questionnaire. According (Sugiyono, 2008), questionnaire is data collection process that is done by giving a set of questions or written statement to the respondent to be answered by the respondent.
2. Documentation Method. According to Arikunto (2002) method of documentation is looking for data about things or variables in the form of notes, transcripts, books, newspapers, magazines, inscriptions, minutes of meetings, agenda and so on.

3.4 Population and Sample

Population

Population of this research is the followers of Bank Syariah Mandiri's Official Fan Page on Facebook on June 2017 (68,004 followers).

Sample

In this study, samples were taken from populations with the Slovin formula (Kriyantoro, 2008)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where n represents sample size; N represents population size; e represents leniency inaccuracy due to sampling errors that can be tolerated and then squared.

This tolerable fault limit for each population is not the same; there are 1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, 5% or 10% (Kriyantoro, 2008). Based on the formula above, then from the number of sample as much as 100 people will be the sample researched.

3.5 Operational Variable

Research variables are attributes or characteristics of people, objects or activities that have certain variations set by the researcher to study and draw conclusions (Sugiyono, 2007). In connection with this research, the research variables consisting of dependent variables and independent variables are described as follows:

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable is the variable that is the center of attention of the researcher (Ferdinand, 2006). The dependent variable is a variable whose value is influenced by an independent variable. What is used as the dependent variable in this study is engagement rate (ER).

1. Independent Variable

Independent variables are variables that affect the dependent variable, both those with positive influence and those with negative influence (Ferdinand, 2006). The independent variables in this study consisted of:

- a. Empathy (E)

- b. Persuasion (P)
- c. Impact (I)
- d. Communication (C)

3.6 Sampling Technique

In this study, the sampling technique uses non probability sampling. According to (Sugiyono, 2008) Non-probability sampling is a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample.

3.7 Data Analysis Technique

3.7.1 Instrumental Test

Validity Test

Validity test is used to measure the validity of a questionnaire (Ghozali, 2009). Valid means the instrument used can measure what it wants to measure (Ferdinand, 2006). A questionnaire is said to be valid if the question on the questionnaire is able to reveal something to be measured by the questionnaire. For example, to measure the engagement rate it consists of three questions, then the question should be able to accurately reveal the rate of engagement. So the validity is to measure whether the question in the questionnaire we have created can really measure what we want to measure.

Validity used in this study is content validity; it describes the suitability of a data meter with what will be measured validity test using Pearson correlation coefficient. In statistics, the Pearson correlation coefficient, also referred to as Pearson's r , the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) or the bivariate correlation is a measure of the linear correlation between two variables X and Y . It has a value between $+1$ and -1 , where 1 is total positive linear correlation, 0 is no linear correlation, and -1 is total negative linear correlation. (Stigler, 1989) The Pearson product-moment correlation formula is as follows:

$$r = r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum y_i^2 - (\sum y_i)^2}}$$

where:

n is the sample size

x^i, y^i , are the single samples indexed with i

\bar{x} is the sample mean; and analogously for \bar{y}

The value of r is then consulted with Pearson's r . If r of the above formula is greater than Pearson's r then the item is valid, and vice versa. (Ferdinand, 2006) The basis of decision to test the validity of the questionnaire is:

- 1) If r positive and r is more than Pearson's r then the variable is valid
- 2) If r negative and r is less than Pearson's r then the variable is invalid

Reliability Test

Cronbach's alpha is a measure used to assess the reliability, or internal consistency, of a set of scale or test items. In other words, the reliability of any given measurement refers to the extent to which it is a consistent measure of a concept, and Cronbach's alpha is one way of measuring the strength of that consistency. (Goforth, 2015) The Cronbach's alpha formula is as follows:

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{k}{k-1} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sigma_{y_i}^2}{\sigma_x^2} \right)$$

where:

k refers to the number of scale items

$\sigma_{y_i}^2$ refers to the variance associated with item

σ_x^2 refers to the variance associated with the observed total scores

The resulting α coefficient of reliability ranges from 0 to 1 in providing this overall assessment of a measure's reliability. If all of the scale items are entirely independent from one another (i.e., are not

correlated or share no covariance), then $\alpha = 0$; and, if all of the items have high covariance, then α will approach 1 as the number of items in the scale approaches infinity. In other words, the higher the α coefficient, the more the items have shared covariance and probably measure the same underlying concept. (Goforth, 2015). According to Ghazali (2009) Cronbach's Alpha can be calculated using computer programming tool such as SPSS for Windows 21 by using Alpha model. An instrument is said to be reliably if the alpha value is greater than 0.600.

3.7.2 Classical Assumption Test

Classical assumption test is done to determine the condition of existing data in order to determine the appropriate model of analysis. To test whether the equation of regression line obtained linear and can be used to forecasting, it must be tested classical assumption that is:

Multicollinearity Test

According to (Ghozali, 2010) Multicollinearity test aims to test whether in the regression model found the existence of correlation between independent variables. A good regression model should not occur correlation between independent variables. If independent variables are mutually correlated, then these variables are not orthogonal is the independent variable whose correlation value among free variables equals zero. Multicollinearity is detected by using tolerance values and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). Tolerance measures the variability of the selected free variables that cannot be explained by other independent variables. So a low tolerance value is equal to a high VIF value (because $VIF = 1 / \text{tolerance}$) and indicates a high collinearity. Common cutoff values used are tolerance values of 0.10 or equal to VIF values below 10. To calculate the multicollinearity, it can be calculated with Pearson correlation coefficient formula, as follow:

$$r = r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum y_i^2 - (\sum y_i)^2}}$$

where:

n is the sample size

x^i, y^i , are the single samples indexed with i

\bar{x} is the sample mean; and analogously for \bar{y}

Normality Test

In statistics, normality tests are used to determine if a data set is well-modeled by a normal distribution and to compute how likely it is for a random variable underlying the data set to be normally distributed.. This test needs to be done because of all parametric statistical calculations. Normally distributed data is that the data will follow the normal distribution form, where the data focuses on mean and median values. The data that form the normal distribution when the amount of data above and below the average is the same, so is the standard deviation.

The next data normality test is to use an analysis of the value of skewness and kurtosis data. Skewness and kurtosis are the more likely sizes to see the distribution of data graphically.

Skewness

Skewness is a measure of symmetry, or more precisely, the lack of symmetry. A distribution, or data set, is symmetric if it looks the same to the left and right of the center point (Filliben, 1975)

Kurtosis

Kurtosis is a measure of whether the data are heavy-tailed or light-tailed relative to a normal distribution. That is, data sets with high kurtosis tend to have heavy tails, or outliers. Data sets with low kurtosis tend to have light tails, or lack of outliers. A uniform distribution would be the extreme case. (Filliben, 1975)

Heteroscedasticity

In statistics, a collection of random variables is heteroscedastic (or heteroskedastic; from Ancient Greek hetero “different” and skedasis “dispersion”) if there are sub-populations that have different variabilities from others. Here "variability" could be quantified by the variance or any other measure of statistical dispersion. Thus heteroscedasticity is the absence of homoscedasticity.

The existence of heteroscedasticity is a major concern in the application of regression analysis, including the analysis of variance, as it can invalidate statistical tests of significance that assume that the modelling errors are uncorrelated and uniform—hence that their variances do not vary with the effects being modeled. For instance, while the ordinary least squares estimator is still unbiased in the presence of heteroscedasticity, it is inefficient because the true variance and covariance are underestimated. (Goldberger, 1964)

3.7.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis is a tool to forecast the value of the influence of two independent variables or more on one dependent variable (to prove the presence or absence of functional relation or causal relation between two or more independent variables).

In this study the use of multiple regression analysis to determine whether there is influence of empathy, persuasion, impact and communication to engagement rate. The equation as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + b_4x_4$$

where;

Y = engagement rate

a = constant

$b_1 - b_4$ = estimated regression coefficients

x_1 = empathy

x_2 = persuasion

x_3 = impact

x_4 = communication

(LaMorte, 2016)

Goodness of Fit Test

The Goodness of Fit test is used to measure the accuracy of the sample regression function in estimating the actual value. Goodness of Fit test can be done by statistical method, which is through measurement of coefficient of determination, F statistic value and t statistic value. According to Ghozali (2009), statistical calculations are called statistically significant if their statistical test scores are in critical areas (areas where H_0 is rejected). Conversely, the statistical calculation is not significant if the value of statistical test is in the area where H_0 accepted.

Correlation Coefficient and Determination Coefficient (R^2)

Ghozali (2009) coefficient of determination (R^2) essentially measures how far the ability of the model in explaining the variation of the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination is between zero and one. A small R^2 value means the ability of independent variables to explain the variation of the dependent variable is very limited. A value close to one means that the independent variables provide almost all the information needed to predict the variation of the dependent variable.

CHAPTER IV:

FINDINGS

4.1 General Description of Research Object

4.1.1 History of Bank Syariah Mandiri

The multi-dimensional crisis that hit Indonesia in 1997-1998 brought a separate lesson to the milestone of the Islamic Banking System in Indonesia. At a time when conventional banks evolved from the economic crisis, at that time there was a growing awareness that concepts that could save from prolonged threats.

On the other hand, to save the global economy, the government took the initiative to merge 4 (four) government-owned banks, namely Bank Dagang Negara, Bank Bumi Daya, Bank Exim and Bapindo, into one, a solid Bank with the name PT Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk. on July 31, 1999. The merger policy also appointed PT Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk as the owner of the entity PT Bank Susila Bakti (BSB). PT BSB is one of the conventional banks conducted by the Employee Welfare Foundation (YKP) of PT Bank Dagang Negara and PT Mahkota Achievement. To get out of the economic crisis, PT BSB also attempted to merge with several other banks and invite foreign investors.

As a follow-up to the thought of the Sharia Economic System Development, the government imposed Law No.10 of 1998 which provides an opportunity for Commercial Banks to present sharia transactions (multiple banking systems). In response, PT Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk calculated and formed the Sharia Banking Development Team, which aims to develop Sharia Banking Services in the PT Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk group.

The Sharia Banking Development Team considers that the enactment of the Law is the right momentum to convert PT Bank Susila Bakti from a Conventional Bank to a Sharia Bank. Therefore, the Sharia Banking Development Team immediately prepares its systems and infrastructure, so that BSB's business activities are transformed from Conventional Banks to Banks operating based on sharia principles under the name of PT Bank Syariah Mandiri as stated in the Notarial Deed: Sutjipto, SH, No. 23 September 8, 1999.

The change in BSB's business activities to become a sharia public bank was confirmed by the Governor of Bank Indonesia through the BI Governor Decree No. 1/24 / KEP.BI/1999, 25 October 1999. Furthermore, through the Decree of the Senior Deputy Governor of Bank Indonesia No.1 / 1 / KEP.DGS / 1999, BI approved the change of name to PT Bank Syariah Mandiri (BSM). Following the inauguration and legal recognition, PT Bank Syariah Mandiri officially began operations since Monday 25th Rajab 1420 H or on 1 November 1999.

PT Bank Syariah Mandiri is present and appears with the harmonization of business idealism with spiritual values. Bank Syariah Mandiri grows as a bank that is able to integrate the two, which underlie its operational activities. This harmonization of business idealism and spiritual values is one of the hallmarks of Bank Syariah Mandiri in its actions in Indonesia.

4.1.2 Bank Syariah Mandiri Business Field

BSM business field based on the latest Amendment Deed Number 2 dated June 2, 2014 approval of the Minister of Law and Human Rights Republic of Indonesia Decree No. AHU-12852.40.22.2014 On June 10, 2014, BSM's Articles of Association are:

- 1 Collecting funds in the form of deposits in the form of Demand Deposits, Savings, or other equivalent forms based on Akad Wadi'ah or other Contracts that are not contrary to Sharia Principles;
- 2 Collecting funds in the form of investments in the form of Deposits, Savings, or other equivalent forms based on mudharabah agreements or other contracts not in conflict with the Sharia principles;
- 3 Distributing profit sharing financing based on Mudharabah, Musyarakah, or other Contracts that do not conflict with Sharia Principles;
- 4 Distributing financing based on murabahah, akad sada, istishna contract or other agreements that do not conflict with Sharia principles;
- 5 Distributing financing based on qardh agreement or other agreements that do not conflict with Sharia principles;
- 6 Distributing financing for the leasing of movable or immovable goods to customers based on the ijarah contract and / or lease purchase in the form

- of ijarah muntahiyabitta owned or other agreements which do not conflict with Sharia Principles;
- 7 Take over debt based on the Hawalah Agreement or other Contracts that are not contrary to Sharia Principles;
 - 8 Conduct business of debit cards and / or financing cards based on Sharia Principles;
 - 9 Buying, selling, or guaranteeing at your own risk third party securities issued on the basis of real transactions based on Sharia Principles, among others, such as Akad ijarah, musyarakah, mudharabah, murabahah, kafalah, or hawalah;
 - 10 Purchase securities based on Sharia Principles issued by the government and / or Bank Indonesia;
 - 11 Receiving payments from bills on securities and calculating with third parties or between third parties based on Sharia Principles;
 - 12 Carry out safekeeping for the interests of other parties based on a contract based on Sharia Principles;
 - 13 Providing a place to store goods and securities based on Sharia Principles;
 - 14 Transferring money, both for its own interests and for customers' interests based on Sharia Principles;
 - 15 Perform functions as Trustee based on the Wakalah contract;
 - 16 Providing letter of credit facilities or Bank guarantees based on Sharia Principles;
 - 17 Conduct other activities commonly carried out in the banking sector and in the social field as long as they do not conflict with the Sharia Principles and in accordance with the provisions of the legislation;
 - 18 Conduct foreign exchange activities based on Sharia Principles;
 - 19 Conducting equity participation activities in Sharia Commercial Banks or financial institutions conducting business activities based on Sharia Principles;
 - 20 Conducting temporary capital participation activities to overcome the consequences of financing failure based on Sharia Principles, provided that they have to withdraw their investments;

- 21 Acting as founder and manager of pension funds based on Sharia Principles; Melakukan kegiatan dalam pasar modal sepanjang tidak bertentangan dengan Prinsip Syariah dan ketentuan peraturan perundang-undangan di bidang pasar modal;
- 22 Carrying out Bank activities or products based on Sharia Principles by using electronic means;
- 23 Publish, offer and trade short-term securities based on Sharia Principles, both directly and indirectly through the money market;
- 24 Publish, offer, and trade in long-term securities based on Sharia Principles, both directly and indirectly through the capital market;
- 25 Providing products or conducting other Sharia Commercial Bank business activities based on Sharia Principles.

4.1.3 Bank Syariah Mandiri Online Presence

Company Website

A website is a web page that contains information or data that can be accessed through an internet network system. As a means of communication, promotion and fulfillment of aspects of good corporate governance, Bank Syariah Mandiri has had a company website since 2000. The Bank Syariah Mandiri website is www.syariahmandiri.co.id Information on the website is presented in Indonesian and English. The content is divided into several things, namely:

- a. Corporate Information
 1. Company profile (History, Profile in the form of bank name, swift code, address, email, share ownership, and supervision authority),
 2. Vision Mission, Shared Values, Organization
 3. Corporate Social Responsibility report,
 4. GCG implementation report in the year concerned,
 5. News and press releases issued by BSM
 6. BSM network which includes outlets and atm,

7. Financial Reports (Monthly, Quarterly, and Annual Report Reports since it was first established in 1999 or more than five years in a row),
 8. Financial Analysis in 2017, and
 9. Sustainability Report, which began in 2013
- b. Information on 24-Hour Services includes BSM Net Banking, Mobile banking services, and BSMCall 14140 call center services. The BSM website is also one of the entrances to internet banking transactions.

c. Consumer Banking

This channel is a channel to inform products in the consumer segment both in terms of funding and financing. Among them includes information about Savings, Current Accounts, deposits, financing products of BSM Griya, BSM Emas, BSM Oto, Products related to Hajj and Umrah, Services and BSM services (Priority).

d. Business Banking

This channel is a channel to inform products and services in the corporate and commercial segments as well as information about products and services in the small and micro segment.

e. Edukasi Syariah

This page contains information about Frequently Asked and Question (FAQ) about Islamic banks and sharia terms and contracts. The content and content on the website are in line with the provisions of the OJK Regulation Number 8 / POJK.04 / 2015 concerning the website of the issuer or public company. Under these provisions, OJK requires companies to provide information in two languages.

The company also opened a corporate e-mail, corsec@bsm.co.id for input or for customer communication channels, either asking questions, opinions, or complaining about Bank services. As of December 2017, the average monthly visits reached more than 121,000. Access to the website is carried out by a majority (60%) via mobile. The information that is widely accessed is sharia investment products and career information.

Based on this, in 2017, BSM has adjusted the appearance of the website to be responsive (adaptive to the media used to access) and will simplify information about the product to be simpler, with a clean design.

Information on Social Media

As the use of the internet is high, especially for social media, Bank Syariah Mandiri also has several official accounts on social media. The official accounts are:

a. Facebook: Bank Syariah Mandiri

Figure IV.1 Bank Syariah Mandiri Facebook Page

As of December 2017 the official Bank Syariah Mandiri fanpage account had 69,491 followers. The account that was first established in 2008 is a means of BSM communication with the community. The information presented includes corporate activities, information on marketing programs, news about BSM, and direct communication with followers. The majority of followers are 65% aged 25-34 years, male and 75% access Facebook via mobile.

b. Twitter: @syariahmandiri

Figure IV.2 Bank Syariah Mandiri Twitter Page

Like Facebook, BSM began communicating via twitter since 2009. As of December 2016, BSM Twitter followers reached 270,797. Communication delivered via Twitter is also information on corporate activities, product promotion, non-formal communication, social activities and others. In addition to corporate Twitter, BSM through its business work unit also has product related accounts including @BSMMenabung and @BSMEmas.

c. Instagram: @BankSyariahMandiri

With 13,317 followers, Instagram account is used to post pictures of corporate activities to followers. As through the official company email corsec@bsm.co.id, BSM social media accounts can also be one of the gateways for customer complaints services. The settlement of customer complaints will be coordinated to the relevant work units through a complaint management system managed by Customer Care.

Figure IV.3 Bank Syariah Mandiri Instagram Page

4.2 Respondent Profile Index

4.2.1 Gender of Respondents

Figure IV.4 Gender of Respondents

Based on the respondents' data that has been obtained, of the total number of respondents, 54% of them were male, and the remaining 46% were female.

4.2.2 Age

Figure IV.5 Age of Respondents

Based on the respondents' data that has been obtained, of the total number of respondents, 43% of them are between the ages of 21-30, 18% of them are aged 31-40, 19% of them are aged 41-50, 11% of them are over 50, and the rest 9% are under 21.

4.2.3 Occupation

Figure IV.6 Occupation of Respondents

Based on the respondents' data that had been obtained, of the total respondents, 21% of them were private company employees, 20% of them

were students, 17% of them were entrepreneurs, 14% of them were housewife, 13% of them were government employees, 9% of them work as lecturers, and others amount to 6%

4.3 Respondent Answer Index

The scale used in this study uses a Likert scale: 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 then the range: $5-1 = 4$, divided into 3 (three) category classes, namely low, medium and high get $4/3 = 1.33$ can be distributed.

Table IV.1 Respondent Answer Index Classes

No	Range	Category
1	1,00-2,33	Low
2	2,34-3,67	Moderate
3	3,68-5,00	High

The answers from 100 respondents to each variable in this study are as follows;

4.3.1 Empathy

Empathy variables in this research are measured through 7 (seven) indicators. Perceptions of empathy according to respondents vary. The results of the answers and indexes of respondents' answers to empathy can be explained as follows:

Table IV.2 Respondent Answer Index - Empathy

Question	Answers					Index	Conclusion
	5	4	3	2	1		
E1	0	0	43	46	11	2,32	Low
E2	0	3	45	41	11	2,40	Moderate
E3	0	1	43	45	11	2,34	Moderate
E4	0	4	46	43	7	2,47	Moderate
E5	0	1	44	47	8	2,38	Moderate
E6	0	1	45	46	8	2,39	Moderate
E7	0	0	44	48	8	2,36	Moderate
Average Index						2,38	Moderate

To find the results of the index of table xx answers which use each indicator variables using the following formula (using the sample variable E1):

$$index = \frac{(0 \times 5) + (0 \times 4) + (43 \times 3) + (46 \times 2) + (11 \times 1)}{100} = \frac{232}{100} = 2,32$$

Based on the table, it can be seen that respondents' responses to empathy are very diverse. The average index score of the answer about empathy obtained is **2,38** and according to the respondents answer index, the score considered as **moderate**.

4.3.2 Persuasion

Persuasion variables in this research are measured through 8 (eight) indicators. Perceptions of persuasion according to respondents vary. The results of the answers and indexes of respondents' answers to persuasion can be explained as follows:

Table IV.3 Respondent Answer Index - Persuasion

Question	Answers					Index	Conclusion
	5	4	3	2	1		
P1	0	3	44	47	6	2,44	Moderate
P2	0	4	44	45	7	2,45	Moderate
P3	0	2	46	47	5	2,45	Moderate
P4	0	3	42	41	14	2,34	Moderate
P5	0	0	45	48	7	2,38	Moderate
P6	0	2	48	45	5	2,47	Moderate
P7	0	4	47	43	6	2,49	Moderate
P8	0	2	43	48	7	2,40	Moderate
Average Index						2,42	Moderate

Based on the table, it can be seen that respondents' responses to persuasion are very diverse. The average index score of the answer about persuasion obtained is **2,42** and according to the respondents answer index, the score considered as **moderate**.

4.3.3 Impact

Impact variables in this research are measured through 7 (seven) indicators. Perceptions of impact according to respondents vary. The results of the answers and indexes of respondents' answers to impact can be explained as follows:

Table IV.4 Respondent Answer Index - Impact

Question	Answers					Index	Conclusion
	5	4	3	2	1		
I1	0	2	43	47	8	2,39	Moderate
I2	0	0	45	47	8	2,37	Moderate
I3	0	2	44	47	7	2,41	Moderate
I4	0	3	44	45	8	2,42	Moderate
I5	0	1	43	46	10	2,35	Moderate
I6	0	2	46	48	4	2,46	Moderate
I7	0	3	47	43	7	2,46	Moderate
Average Index						2,40	Moderate

Based on the table, it can be seen that respondents' responses to impact are very diverse. The average index score of the answer about impact obtained is **2,40** and according to the respondents answer index, the score considered as **moderate**.

4.3.4 Communication

Communication variables in this research are measured through 7 (seven) indicators. Perceptions of communication according to respondents vary. The results of the answers and indexes of respondents' answers to communication can be explained as follows:

Table IV.5 Respondent Answer Index - Communication

Question	Answers					Index	Conclusion
	5	4	3	2	1		
C1	0	2	44	44	10	2,38	Moderate
C2	0	1	44	47	8	2,38	Moderate
C3	0	0	48	48	4	2,44	Moderate
C4	0	3	45	45	7	2,44	Moderate
C5	0	1	46	49	4	2,44	Moderate
C6	0	4	43	40	13	2,38	Moderate
C7	0	3	46	43	8	2,44	Moderate
Average Index						2,41	Moderate

Based on the table, it can be seen that respondents' responses to communication are very diverse. The average index score of the answer about communication obtained is **2,41** and according to the respondents answer index, the score considered as **moderate**.

4.3.5 Engagement Rate

Engagement rate variables in this research are measured through 3 (three) indicators. Perceptions of engagement rate according to respondents vary. The results of the answers and indexes of respondents' answers to engagement rate can be explained as follows:

Table IV.6 Respondent Answer Index - Engagement Rate

Question	Answers					Index	Conclusion
	5	4	3	2	1		
ER1	0	0	40	43	17	2,23	Low
ER2	0	1	46	45	8	2,40	Moderate
ER3	0	0	46	44	10	2,36	Moderate
Average Index						2,33	Low

Based on the table, it can be seen that respondents' responses to engagement rate are very diverse. The average index score of the answer about engagement rate obtained is 2,33 and according to the respondents answer index, the score considered as low.

4.4 Instrumental Test

4.4.1 Validity Test

Validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the question in the questionnaire is able to reveal something that will be measured by the questionnaire (Ghazali, 2011). To find out whether the questions contained in the questionnaire are valid or not, with the following conditions:

$r_{\text{count}} > r_{\text{table}} = \text{valid question}$

$r_{\text{count}} < r_{\text{table}} = \text{invalid question}$

Table IV.7 Validity Test Result

Variables	Items	Table R	Count R	Sig	Note
Empathy	E1	0,195	0,737	0,000	Valid
	E2	0,195	0,703	0,000	Valid
	E3	0,195	0,731	0,000	Valid
	E4	0,195	0,703	0,000	Valid
	E5	0,195	0,756	0,000	Valid
	E6	0,195	0,728	0,000	Valid
	E7	0,195	0,753	0,000	Valid
Persuasion	P1	0,195	0,818	0,000	Valid
	P2	0,195	0,780	0,000	Valid
	P3	0,195	0,738	0,000	Valid
	P4	0,195	0,764	0,000	Valid
	P5	0,195	0,790	0,000	Valid
	P6	0,195	0,804	0,000	Valid
	P7	0,195	0,796	0,000	Valid
	P8	0,195	0,698	0,000	Valid
Impact	I1	0,195	0,819	0,000	Valid
	I2	0,195	0,792	0,000	Valid
	I3	0,195	0,745	0,000	Valid
	I4	0,195	0,769	0,000	Valid
	I5	0,195	0,669	0,000	Valid
	I6	0,195	0,847	0,000	Valid
	I7	0,195	0,810	0,000	Valid
Communication	C1	0,195	0,730	0,000	Valid
	C2	0,195	0,769	0,000	Valid
	C3	0,195	0,908	0,000	Valid
	C4	0,195	0,793	0,000	Valid
	C5	0,195	0,849	0,000	Valid
	C6	0,195	0,789	0,000	Valid
	C7	0,195	0,795	0,000	Valid
Engage ment rate	ER1	0,195	0,820	0,000	Valid
	ER2	0,195	0,857	0,000	Valid
	ER3	0,195	0,846	0,000	Valid

Based on the table it is known that the calculated r value is greater than the r table value ($n = 100$; $\alpha = 5\%$) is equal to 0.195 which indicates that all questions used in this research questionnaire are declared valid and the significance value is below 5% then the question can also be used for further research.

4.4.2 Reliability Test

A questionnaire is said to be reliable or consistent if the answers from the questionnaire are consistent or stable. The reliability test results in this study are;

Table IV.8 Reliability Test Result

Variable	Cut of Value	Cronbach's Alpha	Note
Empathy	0,700	0,853	Reliable
Persuasion	0,700	0,903	Reliable
Impact	0,700	0,891	Reliable
Communication	0,700	0,905	Reliable
Engagement Rate	0,700	0,790	Reliable

Based on the table it is known that the Cronbach's alpha value is greater than Cut of Value in each variable. So it can be concluded that all variables are reliable or consistent.

4.5 Classic Assumption Test

Classic assumption test includes normality test, heteroscedasticity test and multicollinearity test using SPSS 23. The results of the classic assumption test are presented as follows:

4.5.1 Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test aims to test whether the regression model contains correlations between independent variables. A good regression model should not have a correlation between independent variables. Testing whether there are symptoms of multicollinearity is done by observing the VIF value and tolerance value, a regression model is said to be multicollinearity-free if the tolerance value is smaller than 0.10 and the VIF value does not exceed 10. The multicollinearity test results are presented as follows:

Table IV.9 Multicollinearity Test Result

No.	Correlation	Tolerance	VIF	Note
1	E to ER	0,154	6,477	There is no multicollinearity
2	P to ER	0,131	7,653	There is no multicollinearity
3	I to ER	0,125	8,010	There is no multicollinearity
4	C to ER	0,113	8,834	There is no multicollinearity

Based on the table it is known that the VIF value in each variable is less than 10. Then it can be concluded that all variables do not occur multicollinearity.

4.5.2 Normality Test

Normality test aims to determine whether the dependent variable and the independent variable in the regression model have a normal distribution or not.

Table IV.10 Normality Test Result

No	Variable	Skewness Ratio	Kurtosis Ratio	Conclusion
1	Empathy	0.001356822	-1,335478358	Normal
2	Persuasion	-0.442370826	-0,70450757	Normal
3	Impact	-0.228524705	-1,495300544	Normal
4	Communication	-0,24044087	-0.848918914	Normal
5	Engagement Rate	0.199848062	-0.404574042	Normal

According to the provisions of the test for normality, if the value of skewness and kurtosis will be normality if the value of the ratio is between -2 to 2. Based on the table states that the value of skewness and kurtosis on all variables is between the ratio -2 to 2. It can be concluded that the variables E, P, I, C and ER are declared normal so this research can continue.

4.5.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is a variance inequality from residual one observation to another observation.

Table IV.11 Heteroscedasticity Test Result

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	47.163	4	11.791	.550	.601 ^b
Residual	201.823	95	2.124		
Total	248.986	99			

a. Dependent Variable: absresid

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Empati, Impact, Persuasion

Based on the table states that the relationship E,P,I,C to ER by having f count 0,550 and significant value above 0,5 which is 0,601, the conclusion is there is homoscedasticity which means the data are not interfering and influencing each other.

4.6 Determination Coefficient

The test of the coefficient of determination (R^2) is done to see whether there is a perfect relationship or not which is indicated by the change in the independent variable to be followed by the dependent variable in the same proportion. The test results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) in this study are presented as follows

Table 4.12 Coefficient of Determination (R^2) Test Result

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.854 ^a	.730	.719	.906

a. Predictors: (Constant), C_total, I_total, E_total, P_total

As seen in the summary table model the value in column R is 0.854 meaning that the influence of the empathy, persuasion, impact and communication variables on the engagement rate is 85.4% ($0.854 \times 100\%$), but this value could still be contaminated by various possible indicators that caused measurement errors, for that SPSS provides an alternative value of R Square as a comparison of the accuracy of its influence. It can be seen that the R Square value is 0.730 which means 73%. This value is smaller than the R value due to adjustments, however,

as a note, the value is not necessarily smaller than R, but also sometimes larger. For more accurate predictions of our influence can also be based on the value of Adjusted R Square that is the value of the R Square that has been more adjusted and usually the most accurate. It can be seen that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.719 or 71.9% the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The next column in the Model Summary table shows the accuracy of the regression model can be seen in the Standard Error of the Estimate column, there is a number of 0.906. This value is getting closer to the number 0 (zero) the more accurate, with a number as big as it can be said that the accurate formed model is 99.094%.

4.7 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is done to test the decision making proposed in a study. The results of the study can be said to be statistically significant if the event is in accordance with a predetermined probability. The hypothesis is the alleged results of research that might be wrong. The hypothesis is carried out with several tests based on previously processed data.

4.7.1 Partial Test

The partial test is used to see whether the independent variables individually have a significant influence on the dependent variable. Decision making in this partial test is based on the results of t count and t table, if $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ then H_0 can be rejected and vice versa if $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$ then H_0 is accepted. Decision making in partial testing can also be done by looking at significant values (sig.), Where if the sig value. < 0.05 , the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable, and if the sig value. < 0.05 , the independent variable has no significant effect on the dependent variable.

To compare t count and t table values, then t table must be known first. The way to get t table with $\alpha = 0.05$ is:

$$t \text{ table} = \alpha/2; n-k-1$$

$$t \text{ table} = 0,05/2; 100-4-1$$

$$t \text{ table} = 0,025 ; 95$$

t table = 1,66

These are the hypothesis of the study:

H₁ : Empathy positively affects engagement rate

H₂ : Persuasion positively affects engagement rate

H₃ : Impact positively affects engagement rate

H₄ : Communication positively affects engagement rate

H₅ : Empathy, persuasion, impact and communication positively affects engagement rate

Table IV.13 Partial Test Result

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.247	.465		.530	.597
	E_total	-.045	.068	-.090	-.662	.510
	P_total	-.034	.062	-.081	-.547	.586
	I_total	.166	.072	.347	2.302	.024
	C_total	.316	.073	.686	4.327	.000

a. Dependent Variable: ER_total

This table can be used to see the effect per variable. first by looking at the sig value. on each variable, if the value is sig. it is smaller than 0.05, the conclusions affect the smaller sig. the more influential.

Then in this case, **variable impact and communication have a more significant influence on engagement rate than empathy and persuasion.**

The second way is by comparing the t-count value with the t-table, t count is the value in the t column generated by SPSS in the coefficient table while the t-table value that we still have to look for. How to find the value of the t-table, that is, by first calculating the df value, the formula used is different from the anova table, namely $df = n - k - 1$ which is thus calculated $df = 100 - 4 - 1 = 95$.

From the table with df of 95 in the sig. 0.05 we can obtain a t-table value of 1.9852 or 1.985. This value is compared with the value of t count for each variable with criteria, if the t table value is smaller than the calculated t value then the conclusion of this variable influences the dependent variable.

Then, in this case, variable **impact and communication have an influence on engagement rate rather than empathy and persuasion.**

From the Coefficient table, you can also form a Regression Model Equation by looking at the values in the Coefficient B column, which in this case the model is formed:

$$Y = 0,247 + -0,045X_1 + -0,34X_2 + 0,166X_3 + 0,316X_4 + e$$

4.7.2 Simultaneous Test

Table IV.14 Simultaneous Test Result

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	210.945	4	52.736	64.193	.000 ^b
	Residual	78.045	95	.822		
	Total	288.990	99			

a. Dependent Variable: ER_total

b. Predictors: (Constant), C_total, I_total, E_total, P_total

First, look at the Sig. (Significance). In the ANOVA table the sig value. as stated at 0,000, we can easily conclude that the variables of empathy, persuasion, impact and communication have an effect on the engagement rate together. This is by following the sig level. 0.05 as the cut-off value of the significance value. This means that if the probability value (significance) is below 0.05, all independent variables affect the dependent variable and vice versa. The second way is to compare F-Calculate and F-Table. F-table. F-count is the F value generated in the Anova table which is 64.193. After finding F-Calculate then we look for F-Tables, how to find F-Tables that is by first calculating the number of df, df for this test there are two, namely df1 and df2 the formula used is $df1 = k-1$ and $df2 = nk$ where n is the number of samples, k number of independent variables. then the

number $df_1 = 4 - 1 = 3$ and $df_2 = 100 - 4 = 96$. Next we open the statistics book then look for the F distribution table at the sig level. 0.05 which is 2.70 In our case the F-Table value of 2.70 is still smaller than F-Count 64.193, so the conclusion is that **the variables of empathy, persuasion, impact and communication have an influence on the engagement rate. Thus, H_5 is accepted.**

4.8 Findings

This study aims to determine the effect of empathy, persuasion, impact and communication on engagement rate to determine the optimization of social media marketing done by Bank Syariah Mandiri on Facebook Page. The magnitude of the correlation between empathy, persuasion, impact and communication to engagement rate was obtained through regression tests to answer the formulation of the proposed problem as well as to answer the hypotheses proposed.

Test results for each variable can be presented as follows;

4.8.1 The Correlation between Empathy to Engagement Rate

Empathy variable is stated to be **insignificant** with a significance value of 0,510. It means that empathy has an insignificant effect on engagement rate. The regression coefficient of the empathy variable has a **negative value of -0,662**. This shows that the correlation formed between empathy and engagement rate is **negative**. Thus, the first hypothesis is rejected.

The importance of empathy and engagement rate in social media marketing is parallel and cannot be interchangeable. But looking at the respondent answer index data, the empathy variable is low, this supports as the cause why correlation between empathy and engagement rate is low, in Bank Syariah Mandiri Social Media Marketing Case on Facebook Page, and the performance could be optimized and improved.

In social media marketing, social media advertising and social media engagement should go hand in hand. In this case, social media advertising represented by 4 variables, empathy, persuasion, impact and

communication, and social media engagement represented by a dependent variable engagement rate. To improve engagement rate, we need to improve the variables needed to improve social media advertising.

The lack of empathy in social media advertising done by Bank Syariah Mandiri could be seen by the posts they posted each day. Automated and filled with product promotions. It doesn't serve the need of their customer, but does ask people to use their products. In empathy, it is important to make sure that the company knows and caters to the need of their customers. When the customers feel appreciated and fulfilled by the service the company provided through their social media page, the customer will grow emotional bond and loyalty towards the brand, and will eventually increase the engagement rate of the social media marketing. To increase empathy in social media advertising it is advised that Bank Syariah Mandiri begin to humanize their Facebook Page by actually engaging with their customers. When the customers feel welcomed they begin to learn more about the products, and the product knowledge become more efficiently accepted by the customers.

This study supported that emotional appeal attracted higher levels engagement rate, the study conducted by James Kite, Bridget C. Foley, Anne C. Grunseit, and Becky Freeman, titled "Please Like Me: Facebook and Public Health Communication" they stated that posts that featured a positive emotional appeal or provided factual information attracted higher levels of user engagement, while conventional marketing elements, such as sponsorships and the use of persons of authority, generally discouraged user engagement, with the exception of posts that included a celebrity or sportsperson. Their results give insight into post content that maximizes user engagement and begins to fill the knowledge gap on effective use of Facebook by public health organizations. (Kite, Foley, Grunset, & Freeman, 2016)

The significance of product knowledge to increase empathy in social media marketing process is supported by the study conducted by Nidhi

Sinha, Vandana Ahuja and Y. Medury on increasing consumer-brand knowledge directly linked to greater consumer brand loyalty which correlates with empathy. They attempt to find a correlation between variations in consumer-brand knowledge and consumer brand emotion, which clearly indicates that as a consumer's knowledge about a product or brand increases, so does his emotional attachment with the brand. This subsequently increases the consumer adoption of, and relationship with the brand. (Sinha et al., 2011)

4.8.2 The Correlation between Persuasion to Engagement Rate

Persuasion variable is stated to be insignificant with a significance value of 0,586. It means that persuasion has an **insignificant** effect engagement rate. The regression coefficient of the persuasion variable has a **negative value of -0,547**. This shows that the correlation formed between persuasion and engagement rate is **negative**.

Persuasion is an ability to persuade or make people do something because of the information we gave. In this case, persuasion is the ability of Bank Syariah Mandiri to persuade or make their facebook page followers to trust them and to increase their customer's curiosity about Bank Syariah Mandiri's products and services. The correlation between persuasion and engagement rate in this case should be seen as comments asking about more info about the products Bank Syariah Mandiri tries to promote. Based on the study we've conducted, the persuasion is actually insignificant toward engagement rate, meaning that there is little to no comments asking for more info. This might be caused by the oversaturation of information provided by Bank Syariah Mandiri about their products on their Facebook Page.

This is supported by the study conducted by Dokyun Lee, Kartik Hosanagar and Hairkesh S. Nair which titled, "The Effect of Social Media Marketing Content on Consumer Engagement: Evidence from Facebook". They stated that they find that informative content – like mentions of prices, availability, and product features – reduce engagement when included in

messages in isolation, but increase engagement when provided in combination with persuasive attributes. Persuasive content thus seems to be the key to effective engagement. Their results inform content design strategies in social media, and the methodology they develop to content-code large-scale textual data provides a framework for future studies on unstructured natural language data such as advertising content or product reviews. (Lee, Hosanagar, & Nair, 2014)

4.8.3 The Correlation between Impact to Engagement Rate

Impact variable is stated to be **significant** with a significance value of 0,000. It means that impact has a significant effect engagement rate. This means that impact has an important role in engagement rate. The regression coefficient of the impact variable has a **positive value of 4.329**. This shows that what is formed between impact and engagement rate is **positive**.

Impact that we're aiming for is the increase of interest to try the product. After the consumer got persuaded to find out more about the product, they should be lured in to actually try the product. We cannot really measure how much the click through rate of the posts to measure the engagement rate to impact ratio, but according to the study we've conducted, it actually has a significant positive effect.

This is supported by the study conducted by Jean Pusa, titled "Building Brand Awareness through Facebook Adverts - Remarketing. Case Company: Lukoton Experience Ltd.". In this research the impact intended is brand awareness. Based on the launched campaigns, the results are proving that Facebook Advertising can become an effective tool in reaching Lukoton's target audiences in specific domestic area, which is Lahti. Through numbers of reach obtained through Facebook Advertising campaigns, real impact of brand awareness was shown including engagement and page like from chosen audiences.(Pusa, 2017)

The importance of impact and engagement rate in social media marketing is parallel and cannot be interchangeable. But looking at the

respondent answer index data, the impact and engagement variable is rather low, this means that even though the correlation between impact and engagement rate is high, in Bank Syariah Mandiri Social Media Marketing Case on Facebook Page, the performance could be optimized and improved.

4.8.4 The Correlation between Communication to Engagement Rate

Communication variable is stated to be **significant** with a significance value of 0,000. It means that communication has a significant effect engagement rate. This means that communication has an important role in engagement rate. The regression coefficient of the communication variable has a **positive value of 4.329**. This shows that what is formed between communication and engagement rate is **positive**.

Communication is a way to inform and to receive information. In this case, Bank Syariah Mandiri provides the information about their products and how their consumers as the followers give information such as feedbacks and reviews. The study we've conducted shows that the correlation between communication and engagement rate is significant. It can be shown as reviews that being left by the followers on Bank Syariah Mandiri's Facebook Page.

The importance of communication and engagement rate in social media marketing is parallel and cannot be interchangeable. But looking at the respondent answer index data, the communication and engagement variable is rather low, this means that even though the correlation between communication and engagement rate is high, in Bank Syariah Mandiri Social Media Marketing Case on Facebook Page, the performance could be optimized and improved.

CHAPTER V: CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion

This study was conducted to measure the optimization of Facebook Page as Social Media Marketing done by Bank Syariah Mandiri. We've conducted it by measuring the correlation between Social Media Advertising Variables from the EPIC Model by Nielsen, as the independent variable which consist of Empathy, Persuasion, Impact and Communication, to Social Media Engagement variable which is engagement rate as the dependent variable.

The result shows us that there's still a lot of room to improve to optimize the social media marketing strategy done by Bank Syariah Mandiri to increase the engagement rate and social media advertising success on Facebook Page. For example, in Empathy, its insignificance shows us that we can improve it by creating contents that induce emotional impact towards the viewers so that they become more emotionally attached to the brand. Etc.

Based on the result of the study measuring the social media marketing optimization by looking at the correlation between EPIC variables to engagement rate that we've conducted and discussed in chapter four. We draw the following conclusions;

1. Empathy has a negative and insignificant effect on engagement rate
2. Persuasion has a negative and insignificant effect on engagement rate
3. Impact has a positive and significant effect on engagement rate
4. Communication has a positive and significant effect on engagement rate
5. All of the EPIC variables altogether have a significant and positive effect to Engagement Rate. This can be seen from the test results obtained by f table of 64,193 and a significance level of 0,000

5.2 Research Limitations

In conducting this research, we have found many limitations, including:

1. This study still doesn't reveal the full insight of the optimization of Bank Syariah Mandiri Facebook Page as a Social Media Marketing platform because of the limited resource that can only be accessed by the internal management of Bank Syariah Mandiri, mainly the Facebook Analytics data, which consist of vital indicators such as, Click Through Rate (CTR), Bounce Rate, Engagement Rate, and Return on Investment (ROI)
2. There's a few to none previous study to refer about the correlation between Social Media Advertising and Engagement to measure Social Media Marketing optimization.
3. This research is only limited to using multiple linear regression.

5.3 Suggestions.

For Bank Syariah Mandiri

Suggestion for Bank Syariah Mandiri, is that the main problem that we find in this case is that the Bank Syariah Mandiri's online presence is too static and automated. This can be further improved by assigning a team to be dedicated to maintain their social media presence. Not only on Facebook but also on other platform such as Twitter, Instagram, etc. The other thing that could be considered is to work with marketing agencies to let them maintain it and the agency will give the company the insight and full report monthly and even annually.

To increase empathy in social media advertising, we suggested trying for "story-telling" type of content. It induces empathy, and it makes people feel they could relate to. Give the audience something to relate to, and something worth re-sharing. It could be a motivational story about a customer who have been through hard times, but because of the product he used in BSM he could survive, etc. Make a story that could motivate people, and make people feel like they could trust the brand.

To increase persuasion, it is important to make sure that the content shared is worth liking or sharing, because we will need to persuade our audience to like/share the content we posted. This could be done by making an educational post, fun facts or motivational quotes, and most importantly is to ask your audience to like or share it.

To maintain impact and communication, it is important to keep the product promotion updated once in a while, but it is even better if it is well-placed and well-timed. Because of the automation, the product promotion posts are too over-saturated and too often that people start treating it as an advertisement so they would skip right through it. Even though the goal of making an impact and creating communication is a success, but it could be improved by improving the quality of the content and the timing of the posts.

For Researchers

It is important to conduct a further research regarding engagement rate with deeper insight and data about Social Media Marketing Strategy, especially on Facebook and Instagram. Because, researching the outer layer like this could only give us a general insight about what the audience think about the Social Media Marketing Strategy but not so much about how the company or brand has been doing statistically.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Aaker, D. A. (2008). *Strategic Market Management*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
- Aasheim, H., & Stensønes, I. (2011). *Financial Institutions in Social Media; Deliver Traditional Services in New Channels. A Case Study Of Danske Bank*. Copenhagen Business School, Copenhagen.
- American Marketing Association, (AMA). (2013). Definition of Marketing. Retrieved August 25, 2017, from www.ama.org/AboutAMA/Pages/Definition-of-Marketing.aspx
- Arifia, R. (2016). Social Media Optimization (SMO) to Improve Islamic Banks' Marketing. *Jurnal Ekonomi. Dan Bisnis Islam Universitas Airlangga*, 2(1).
- Arikunto, S. (2002). *Prosedur Penelitian: Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.
- Carlson, N. (2010, March 5). At Last -- The Full Story Of How Facebook Was Founded [News Website]. Retrieved September 7, 2017, from www.businessinsider.com/how-facebook-was-founded-2010-3/?IR=T
- Chan, D. (2000). Air wars in Asia: Competitive and collaborative strategies and tactics in action. *Journal of Management Development*, 19(6).
- Chapra, M. U. (1985). *Towards a Just Monetary System*. International Institute of Islamic Thought (IIIT).
- Chikandiwa, S. T., Contogiannis, E., & Edgar, J. (2013). The adoption of social media marketing in South African banks. *European Business Review*, 25(4), 365–381. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-02-2013-0013>
- Constine, J. (2017, June 27). Facebook now has 2 billion monthly users... and responsibility [News Website]. Retrieved September 7, 2017, from techcrunch.com/2017/06/27/facebook-2-billion-users/

- Conte, C. (2012). *How to improve sales promotion effectiveness: the role of age and product category*. Università Ca' Foscari Venezia.
- Davis, M. F. (2015, July 14). Facebook Close Sets Speed Record for \$250 Billion Market Cap [News Website]. Retrieved September 7, 2015, from www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2015-07-13/facebook-s-close-sets-speed-record-for-250-billion-market-value
- De Chernatony, L., & McDonald, M. H. . (1992). *Creating Powerful Brands*. Butterworth- Heinemann, Oxford & Boston.
- Durianto, D. (2003). *Invasi Pasar dengan Iklan Yang Efektif*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Ferdinand, A. (2006). *Metodelogi Penelitian Manajemen*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Fill, C. (2002). *Marketing Communications; contexts, strategies and applications* (3rd ed.). Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
- Filliben, J. J. (1975). The Probability Plot Correlation Coefficient Test for Normality. *Technometrics*, 17(1).
- Fournier, S., & Avery, J. (2011). The uninvited brand. *Business Horizon*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.001>
- Ghozali, I. (2010). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan SPSS*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Goforth, C. (2015). Using and Interpreting Cronbach's Alpha [Online Library]. Retrieved September 20, 2017, from <https://data.library.virginia.edu/using-and-interpreting-cronbachs-alpha/>
- Goi, C.-L. (2014). The Impacts of Social Media on the Local Commercial Banks in Malaysia. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 19(1). Retrieved from www.arraydev.com/commerce/jibc/
- Goldberger, A. S. (1964). *Economic Theory* (10th ed.). John Wiley.

- Grönroos, C. (2007). *Service management and marketing: customer management in service competition* (3rd ed.). Chichester: John Wiley & Sons.
- Hajirnis, A. (2015). Social Media Networking: Parent Guidance Required. *The Brown University Child and Adolescent Behavior Letter*, 31(12), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbl.30086>
- Johnson, G., Scholes, K., & Whittington, R. (2008). *Exploring Corporate Strategy – Text & Cases*. Prentice Hall, Pearson Education.
- Jones, B. (2010). Entrepreneurial marketing and the web 2.0 interface. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.1108/14715201011090602>
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizon*, 53(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003>
- Kartajaya, H. (2007a). *Hermawan Kartajaya on Process*. Mizan Pustaka.
- Kartajaya, H. (2007b). *Hermawan Kartajaya on Selling*. Mizan Pustaka.
- Kite, J., Foley, B. C., Grunset, A. C., & Freeman, B. (2016). Please Like Me: Facebook and Public Health Communication. *PLoS ONE*.
- Kotler, P. (2000). *Marketing Management* ((Millenium Edition), Custo Edition for University of Phoenix). Prentice Hall.
- Kotler, P., & Amstrong, G. (2001). *Principles of Marketing* (9th ed.). New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing Management* (14th, Illustrated ed.). Pearson.
- Kriyantoro, R. (2008). *Teknik Praktis Riset Komunikasi (disertai contoh praktis riset media public relations, advertising komunikasi organisasi, komunikasi pemasaran)*. Jakarta: PT Kencana.

- LaMorte, W. W. (2016). Multiple Linear Regression Analysis [Online Library]. Retrieved September 20, 2018, from http://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/MPH-Modules/BS/BS704-EP713_MultivariableMethods/
- Lanchester, J. (2017). You Are the Product. *London Review of Books*, 39(16). Retrieved from www.lrb.co.uk/v39/n16/john-lanchester/you-are-the-product
- Law, J., & Pallister, J. (2009). *A Dictionary of Business and Management* (5th ed.). OUP Oxford.
- Lee, D., Hosanagar, K., & Nair, H. S. (2014). The Effect of Social Media Marketing Content on Consumer Engagement: Evidence from Facebook.
- Lynch, R. (2000). *Corporate Strategy*. Harlow: Financial Times/Pitman.
- Mangold, W. G., & Faulds, D. J. (2009). Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix. *Business Horizon*, 52(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.03.002>
- Mayshak, R., Sharman, S. J., Zinkiewicz, L., & Hayley, A. (2017). The influence of empathy and self-presentation on engagement with social networking website posts.
- McCarthy, E. J. (1960). *Basic Marketing: A Managerial Approach*. Homewood, Illinois: Richard D. Irwin.
- Middleton, V. T. C., & Clarke, J. (2001). *Marketing in Travel and Tourism* (3rd ed.). Oxford: Butterworth-Heineman.
- Mitic, M., & Kapoulas, A. (2012). Understanding the role of social media in bank marketing. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 30(7), 668–686. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02634501211273797>
- Nasution, F. S. P., & Suyanto, A. (2016). The Effectiveness of Social Media Advertising Using EPIC AC Nielsen on Cellular Operators in Indonesia. *E-Proceeding of Management*, 3(3).
- Nazir, M. (2003). *Metode Penelitian*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

- Park, D.-B., & Yoon, Y.-S. (2009). Segmentation by motivation in rural tourism: A Korean case study. *Tourism Management*, 30(1), 99–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2008.03.011>
- Porterfield, A., Khare, P., & Vahl, A. (2013). *Facebook Marketing All-In-One For Dummies* (2nd ed.). New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Pusa, J. (2017). *Building Brand Awareness through Facebook Adverts - Remarketing. Case Company: Lukoton Experience Ltd.* Haaga-Helia University of Applied Sciences, Finland.
- Rakhmat, J. (2004). *Metode Penelitian Komunikasi*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Schenck, B. F. (2005). *Small Business Marketing for Dummies* (2nd ed.). Indianapolis, Indiana: Wiley Publishing, Inc.
- Schivinski, B., & Dabrowski, D. (2013). *The effect of social-media communication on consumer perceptions of brands* (Working Paper). Gdansk University of Technology, Poland.
- Sherman, A., & Smith, D. E. (2013). *Social Media Engagement For Dummies*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Singh, S. (2010). *Social Media Marketing for Dummies*. Ontario: John Wiley & Sons Canada, Ltd.
- Sinha, N., Ahuja, V., & Medury, Y. (2011). Corporate blogs and internet marketing – Using consumer knowledge and emotion as strategic variables to develop consumer engagement. *Macmillan Publishers, Ltd.*, 18(3).
- Statista. (2017, August). Most famous social network sites worldwide as of August 2017, ranked by number of active users (in millions) [Statistic and Study Portal]. Retrieved September 7, 2017, from www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users/

- Sugiyono. (2008). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sula, M. S., & Kartajaya, H. (2006). *Syariah Marketing*. Mizan Pustaka.
- Tuten, T. L., & Solomon, M. R. (2014). *Social Media Marketing* (2nd ed.). SAGE.
- Uggla, H. (2006). *Positionering-Teori, trend & strategi*. Malmö: Liber.
- Umar, H. (2003). *Riset Pemasaran Dan Perilaku Konsumen*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Waterschoot, W. van, & Bulte, C. van den. (1992). The 4P Classification of the Marketing Mix Revisited. *American Marketing Association*, 56(No. 4).
- Welch, C. (2017, June 27). Facebook crosses 2 billion monthly users [News Website]. Retrieved September 7, 2017, from www.theverge.com/2017/6/27/15880494/facebook-2-billion-monthly-users-announced
- Wigmo, J., & Wikström, E. (2010). *Social Media Marketing* (Bachelor Thesis). Linnaeus University, Ljungby.